

MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF "SAFFIL"/AA6061 METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A comparison is made between microstructures produced by a powder metallurgy route and a liquid pressure infiltration route for AA6061 aluminium alloy composites with 15v% Saffil short fibres. Macrohardness measurements on these composites were carried out to determine the T6 heat treatment conditions. Tensile properties were assessed at room and elevated temperatures up to 350°C. Fracture surfaces were examined and the fracture mode discussed. The results enable the properties of these composites to be correlated with the process route and the resultant microstructures.

1. INTRODUCTION

MMCs consisting of short alumina fibres, for example RF grade Saffil fibres, in aluminium based alloys have been the subject of extensive study in recent years [1-3]. These composites have exhibited a high performance potential in terms of, for example, specific stiffness, tensile strength over a range of temperature, and wear resistance, etc.. However, difficulties in developing viable fabrication routes have limited their commercial exploitation.

The objective of the present paper is to outline some results from studies into the fabrication techniques, microstructure, tensile properties and fracture mechanisms of an Al alloy (AA6061) based composite containing the Saffil (δ phase alumina) fibres.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 MATERIALS AND FABRICATION

The 6061Al alloy was used as matrix material in this project and it contained 1.14% Mg, 0.66% Si, 0.3% Cu, 0.33% Fe, 0.2% Cr, 0.007% Mn, with the balance Al. The Saffil fibres contained about 3 to 4 wt.% SiO₂ which is dispersed throughout the fibre section. The original mean diameter of the fibre was about $\sim 3\mu\text{m}$, and the length about $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$.

A powder metallurgy route and a liquid pressure infiltration technique were used for manufacturing the MMCs. In both methods, the volume fraction of the Saffil fibres was kept at 15v%. To achieve a uniform blend of fibre and prealloyed metal powder by the PM route, a T2C Turbula mixer was used in the first stage, which was then followed by dry processing in a

modified CGM 100 Blast Mill to disperse the fibre tangles and reduce the fibre length. This was not a grinding or milling operation, but should regard as a high energy sieving stage as described in detail elsewhere^[4]. After blending, the powders were canned and degassed, followed by hot-pressing in closed and open dies on a 200-ton capacity Fielding hydraulic press, with a total reduction of >40%, at ~570°C. The composite produced by this PM route, was coded as PM.F. The Liquid Pressure Infiltration technique was performed by Cray Advanced Materials. This technique has been described by Mykura [1]. In this processing, the fibre reinforced materials were manufactured using preheated fibre preforms produced by suction of fibre slurries over a porous mould. The injection of liquid 6061Al alloy was carried out under a pressure of 25 bar, at 560°C. The composite processed via this method was coded as LPI.F.

After fabrication, representative samples were cut and polished for optical microscopy, to provide microstructural information.

2.2. AGEING HEAT TREATMENT

To determine the T6 (artificial peak aged) heat treatment condition, the as-fabricated samples were solutionised at 530°C ± 5°C for two hours, ice water quenched, and aged in an oil bath at 175°C, for various times. The ageing response was monitored via hardness measurements, by using a 10 kg load on a Vickers macrohardness machine. Hardness readings reported for ageing curve fitting are the average of five indentations, and had an error of ± 3VHN.

2.3. MECHANICAL TESTING

All the specimens for mechanical testing were machined from the materials in the as-fabricated condition, and were then subjected to a T6 ageing heat treatment. Cylindrical tensile specimens with a 45mm gauge length and 7mm diameter, were prepared in accordance with BS18:1987. The tensile experiments were performed on an Instron universal testing machine, using a cross head speed of 1 mm min⁻¹. The machine was equipped with a specially designed environmental chamber which has a maximum temperature of 600°C. Elevated temperature tensile testing was conducted over a temperature range of 150°C - 350°C by heating the specimens for 60 min, with approximately 15 min required for heat-up and the remaining 45 min used for soaking at the specified test temperature.

After the mechanical test, fracture surfaces of the specimens were examined on a Philips PSEM 500 scanning electron microscope operated at 25kV.

3. RESULTS

3.1 MICROSTRUCTURES

3.1.1 Microstructure of PM Route Fabricated Composite (PM.F).

A representative optical microstructure of the composite manufactured by the PM route, in the as-hot pressed condition, is shown in Fig.1. Some clusters of Saffil fibres are observed; however, the macroscopic distribution was fairly regular, and the orientation of the reinforcement component was random. The prior particle boundaries of the aluminium powder appear to be decorated by the remaining fragments of the aluminium oxide skin. Fibre breakage by this route seems quite significant. The measurement of the

Fig.1 Microstructure of PM.F composite

dimensions on the extracted fibres showed that the fibre length was reduced considerably from 50~100 μm (original) to about 10~20 μm average. A small degree of porosity was visible around some fibres. However, the total volume fraction of porosity remained low (<2%).

In previous work [5], it has been shown that there was no interaction layer on the Saffil/Al interface except some small Al-Fe-Cr-Si intermetallic particles ($\sim 0.1\mu\text{m}$) which were observed equally in the matrix.

3.1.2. Microstructure of Liquid Pressure Infiltration Processed Composite (LPI.F).

Little relative fibre motion occurs during the liquid pressure infiltration process of LPI.F composites. The planar random nature of the fibre distribution, which was essentially inherited from the preform, is quite clearly seen in optical micrograph Fig.2. A relatively high proportion of coarse second phases were found in this LPI.F composite, as indicated at I in Fig. 2. They are normally solute-enriched, and tend to grow radially from the Saffil fibre into the matrix and often formed a bridge between fibres. Except for these second phases, no significant chemical reaction products containing Mg were detected on the Saffil fibre/Al interface. Fibre breakage in this liquid pressure infiltration process seems to be not so severe as that in PM route. The average length was found to be reduced to about 20 ~ 30 μm .

Another microstructural difference between the LPI.F and PM.F products is that the porosity content was much higher in the former. One example of the porosity morphology is given in an SEM micrograph, Fig.3. The overall porosity content was approximately between 1%~4% in the LPI.F composite.

3.2 AGEING HEAT TREATMENT

The ageing curve obtained for the PM.F composite, together with its corresponding unreinforced alloy, which underwent the same processing history, is illustrated in Fig.4. At an ageing temperature of 175 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the peak ageing time for the composite is about 4hr., which is less than that for the unreinforced alloy (8~10hr.).

For the LPI.F composites, the overall hardness data were very scattered, and the variation seemed to be random in different areas. Fig.5 shows two examples of the distribution of individual hardnesses at selected ageing times. The peak ageing time which was estimated by the average hardness data, is between 6 and 8hr. Since no corresponding unreinforced alloy fabricated by the same route was available, it was not possible to determine whether the age-hardening of the matrix in this LPI.F composite was impaired or improved.

Fig.2 Microstructure of LPI.F composite (a). Vertical section, (b). Horizontal section I: Second phase

Fig. 3 Morphology of porosity (arrow P) in LPI.F composite (SEM).

Fig. 4 Ageing curves of PM.F composite and its corresponding unreinforced alloy.

Fig. 5. Frequency distribution of individual hardness impressions in LPI.F composite.

3.3 TENSILE PROPERTIES

The tensile test results are summarised in Table 1. For the PM.F materials, the results in the Table are averages of three valid tests. For the LPI composites, the measured strength and elongation was quite scattered, and individual rather than average values of these properties are recorded in Table 1.

Table 1 Summary of tensile test results

Material	Temperature (°C)	Modulus (GPa)	0.2% Proof Stress (MPa)	U.T.S. (MPa)	Total Plastic Elongation (%)
PM.F	20	86	360	382	0.8
	150	75	306	320	0.9
	200	72	239	250	1.1
	250	67	167	175	2.0
	300	60	103	107	3.0
	350	55	63	66	5.2
LPI.F	25	82	272	300	0.7
			-	255	-
			230	275	1.1
	150	not calculated	173	220	1.1
			-	209	0.7
			-	150	0.9
200	-	101	110	1.4	
350	-	55	68	1.9	

Compared with the PM route MMCs, the tensile modulus and strength of the liquid pressure infiltration processed composite are relatively poor. The ductility of both composites is generally low at room temperature (< 2%), although it increased monotonically with the increase of temperature in the selected testing temperature range. The effect of temperature on the ultimate tensile strength of the tested material is illustrated in Fig.6. The unreinforced 6061Al alloy included in this figure has the same processing history as PM.F composite.

Fig. 6. Effect of temperature on the ultimate tensile strength of the materials tested.

3.4 FRACTURE SURFACES OF TENSILE TESTED SPECIMENS

A detailed SEM examination was conducted on the fracture surfaces of the tensile tested specimens. Representative fractographs are presented in Fig.7. Those from samples after elevated temperature testing are given in Fig.8.

At room temperature, the common fracture features of the PM.F sample include both cleavage facets and dimples (Fig.7(a)). Some fibres lying perpendicular to the tensile axis (i.e., in the transverse direction) are seen to have been separated from the surrounding matrix during the fracture process. Close examination of the exposed fibres shows that there is a residual thin film of aluminium on their surfaces. The fibres in the longitudinal direction were well embedded in the matrix.

The fracture surface of the liquid infiltrated composite sample (Fig.7(b)) is covered by a large quantity of circular voids of about the size of the fibre diameter, i.e. $\sim 3\mu\text{m}$. It appears that these voids are associated with fibre reinforcement lying in tensile axis direction. Secondary cracks were seen to be associated with the intermetallics, as shown at S, Fig. 7 (b).

Fig.8 shows the fractographs of these fibre reinforced composite samples tested at elevated temperature. At 250°C , the fracture surface of the PM.F sample (Fig.8(a)) shows a much more well-defined rupture than that at room temperature. At 350°C , the fracture surface remained more or less similar to that at 250°C , as shown in (Fig.8(b)). In the LPI.F sample (Fig.8(c)), dimples on the fracture surface appeared much larger. In many instances, serpentine glide lines were present on the wall of the dimples, as at L in Fig.8(c).

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 MICROSTRUCTURAL STUDIES.

One of the main problems in the production of short fibre MMCs using a PM route is the physical blending of the short fibres with the metal powder matrix. The patented blending method used in the present project seems able to overcome this problem quite well, and macro segregation of fibres was avoided. The low level of porosity in the PM.F materials suggests that the parameters of hot-pressing were also well selected and combined. The absence of any excessive reaction layer may be attributed to the low temperature and short duration involved in the hot-pressing process.

In the composite produced by the liquid pressure technique, the existence of pores at the interface of the Saffil/Al indicates that the chemistry in the present system may not be ideal for achieving good wetting of the Saffil fibres, or that the applied pressure (perhaps assisted by capillary forces), may not be high enough to overcome the resistance to penetration of the melt through the fibre network. The coarse solute-rich second phases associated with fibre/Al interfaces could be caused by solidification of last liquid in the vicinity of the Saffil surface^[6].

4.2 AGEING BEHAVIOUR

The hardness results show that the PM route produced fibre composite needed less time to reach the peak ageing value than the corresponding unreinforced alloy ($\sim 4\text{hr.}$ vs. $\sim 8\text{hr.}$). This accelerated ageing phenomena suggested that the segregation of magnesium at the interface, if this indeed occurred, was not significant in the present PM route composites.

The scattering of hardness in the LPI.F composite material could be caused by local variations in the volume fraction of the hard phases, such as fibres and intermetallic phases, and β' Mg_2Si precipitates. During fabrication, the possible participation of Mg in the interfacial reactions in this liquid pressure infiltration route^[7], would cause depletion of Mg in some localised areas in the matrix, and hence result in the variation of precipitation volume fraction and the consequent local age hardening response.

Fig.7 Representative fracture surfaces of present Saffil/Al composites at room temperature. (a). PM.F sample, (b). LPI.F sample, A: exposed fibre; S: secondary cracking

Fig.8 Fracture surfaces of tested composites at elevated temperature.

- (a). PM.F sample tested at 250°C,
 - (b). PM.F sample tested at 350°C,
 - (c). LPI.F sample tested at 350°C,
- L: serpentine glide lines

4.3 ANALYSIS OF TENSILE PROPERTIES

In the LPI.F samples, although the fibre breakage was less severe than that which occurred during fabrication of the PM.F material, the presence of both porosity and coarse second phases at the interface could result in a weaker interfacial bonding and a lower interface load transfer capability than in the PM.F composite. Therefore lower modulus and strength values were observed in the LPI.F specimen, since interfacial load transfer is critical to the achievement of high modulus and strength in the fibre reinforced composite. However, it is found that the tensile test results obtained from both routes compare favourably with the data of similar composites reported in the literature [2, 8]. The scattering of the tensile properties of the LPI.F composite samples, as in the case of the hardness, should be attributed mainly to the inhomogenous distribution of fibres and precipitates.

The effect of temperature on the strength observed in this experiment was also similar to the trend reported by other workers [9, 10]. Fig.6 shows that the higher strength level of the PM.F composite over the LPF.I composite is maintained up to a medium temperature of $\sim 200^{\circ}\text{C}$. This indicated that improving the fibre/Al interfacial bonding condition is also very important for obtaining a higher strength capability at elevated temperatures. However, above 300°C , the fibre seemed no longer able to offer any additional strengthening in these composites, due mainly to stress relaxation, and the composite strength was totally dominated by that of the matrix. Therefore, at 300°C or above, the strength difference between the PM.F and the LPI.F composites becomes insignificant, and approached gradually the strength level of the unreinforced alloy.

4.4 FRACTURE BEHAVIOUR

At room temperature, for the tensile tested PM.F samples, the observed residual thin aluminium film attached to the exposed transverse fibre surface suggests that weak interfacial bonding may not be the principle factor causing separation. This could be due to the existence of a high stress concentration. On the one hand, some clusters of fibres, or fibres touching each other, were observed, and this will lead to a stronger tendency to induce stress localisation. On the another hand, the characteristic fibre geometry includes a sharp corner profile which favours the concentration of stress during loading. During tensile testing, voids nucleated at the fibre corners were often found. This phenomenon has also been reported by other researchers [11]. These voids could grow towards the centre of the fibre interface (Fig. 7(a)), and thus cause the subsequent interfacial separation. However, in the LPI.F material, some of the fibre/Al interface bonding does seem quite weak. One indication of this is that clean surfaces of some of the fibres are exposed on the fracture surface (A, Fig.6(b)). The weak interfacial bonding could be caused by the locally incomplete infiltration, or shrinkage porosity, as has been shown in the micrograph, Fig. 3. Moreover, the second phases, which are connected with the fibre surfaces also played an important role. They often served as stress raisers, leading to the promotion of secondary microcracks (S, Fig.6 (b)), and would also facilitate interface decohesion. The microdimples on the fracture surfaces, which were approximately the same diameter as the fibres, could result from the growth and coalescence of multiple voids nucleated at the fibre ends, or by pulling out of the fibres lying in the tensile direction.

As the temperature was progressively raised, strain localisation decreased, plastic accommodation at the fibres became much easier, and the voids or microcracks nucleated later. Elongation to failure was thus observed to increase with an increase of temperature within the selected temperature range.

The examination of the fracture surface shows that the void nucleation, growth and coalescence failure mechanism became much more significant at elevated temperatures. The incidence of brittle fracture features, such as longitudinal fibre breakage and transverse fibre interface separation, gradually disappeared at testing temperatures above 250°C . This may be due to the relief of residual stress and the occurrence of dislocation climb during deformation. It was mentioned above that in the LPI.F fibre reinforced composites, pre-existing porosity and fibre surface connected coarse second phases were conducive to crack nucleation, and facilitated interfacial decohesion. The precise role of these microstructural factors in the fracture process at elevated temperatures is not clear. It appears that voids nucleating at fibre ends are more

prevalent at elevated temperatures than at room temperature. Serpentine lines on the walls of the dimples indicated large amounts of shearing at or near the interface, which occurred during high temperature tensile deformation, and could account for the increased ductility.

5. CONCLUSION

1. In the manufacture of short Saffil fibre reinforced AA6061 metal matrix composites, with the Powder Metallurgy route used in the present project, Saffil fibres were reasonably well dispersed with no macroscopic inhomogeneity, and extensive ceramic/matrix interface reaction was avoided. The Liquid Pressure Infiltration technique used by Cray Advanced Materials appears to be less mature at this stage. Primary differences in the microstructure compared with that obtained by the PM route, are a much higher degree of porosity and coarse second phases associated with fibre surfaces. However, the damage of fibres was less severe.

2. The peak ageing time for the PM composites was about 4~6hr., which is less than that of the unreinforced alloy (8~10hr.). The ageing hardness data of the liquid pressure infiltrated products is quite scattered due to the less homogenous solute concentration and possible interface Mg segregation. The ageing time of the LPI.F to reach the average peak hardness was around 6~8hr.

3. With the present fabrication conditions, the tensile properties of the LPI.F composite, such as the modulus and strength, seemed to be inferior to those of the PM.F composite. However, these properties of both PM.F and LPI.F composites are comparable to the data of similar composites reported in the literature at both room and elevated temperatures.

4. In these fibre reinforced composites, the fracture mode was very complicated. In the PM.F case, fracture often started by fibre failure, particularly where fibres were flawed during fabrication or clustered together. In the liquid infiltration processed composites, porosity and fibre connected coarse second phases played important roles in the fracture process. They often served as stress raisers, leading to the promotion of secondary microcracks, which facilitated interface decohesion, and were responsible for the observed inferior tensile properties. However, this fracture mechanism seems less pronounced at elevated temperature.

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